

THE PUN AS A STYLISTIC DEVICE AND ITS USE IN LITERARY TEXT

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to investigation of the pun, its structure and semantic meaning. Theoretical content of the article is proved by examples.

A pun is a stylistic speech revolution that is based on ambiguity, generated homonymy or similarity of words that may have different meanings. The linguistic style there is a debate about a single understanding of the essence of a pun, which is also manifested in terminological diversity. This technique is often referred to as "pun", "verbal acuity", "double meaning". The pun is different from other types of wordplay by the presence of two important components: multiplicity and humorous and satirical effect. Among the puns can be identified: the clash of homophones; consonance of words in a narrow context; comparison of homonyms, homographs; destruction and transformation of stable phrases and idioms; polysemy of a word or phrase; comic etymology, etc.

According to this typology, a pun can be:

- a) speech flow. In this case, it is considered without separating it from the context on which its translation depends; this complicates the task of the translator, but at the same time serves as a scope for finding the most successful solution;
- b) an independent work, a miniature related to the epigram;
- c) heading. The pun-title is the ideological content of the work, expressing the exact intention of the author, and this, due to the lack of context, is quite difficult to convey when translating.

Pun – stylistic of speech based on using different values comic identical or similar sounding (graphic design) words as well as at different values of one and the same of said units. The result of such use are semantically multifaceted texts, characterized by humorous or satirical orientation [3, p. 45].

Pun can be as an independent work, and part of it.

For a better understanding of the structural and semantic features of the pun, the convenience of description of its structure and informative ways to recreate other languages by means of the work is considered the general structure of a pun.

The classification of pun worked out by the Chinese scholar Yuan Chuandao is different. He claims that the creation of pun is connected not only to the meaning and the homophony of a word, but also to the context, manner of speech and logic. So he singles out the following types of pun:

1. Homonymic pun (identical sounds and spelling);
2. Lexical meaning pun (polysemantic words);
3. Understanding pun (through the particular context implied meaning of a sentence is revealed).
4. Figurative pun (a simile or a metaphor as its surface meaning and the figurative meaning as its deep meaning).
5. Logic pun (a rhetorical device, a kind of implication in a particular context). As research revealed a pun is one of the most important types of wordplay [2, p. 78].

There are several subcategories of pun and consequently its various classifications and types are formulated by different scholars. On the basis of the mentioned types and various classifications of pun and the analysis of the empirical material examples in the article, a new classification form of pun including all the main types of pun is introduced below:

1. Lexical-Semantic Pun;
2. Structural-Syntactic Pun;
3. Structural-Semantic Pun.

As pointed out by Raskin, pun (one of the forms of wordplay) could be considered as one of the varieties of a joke (anecdote), as its semantic structure is characterized by juxtaposition of two similar but opposite scripts. [1, p.45].

Structural-Syntactic Pun

Structural – syntactic ambiguity arises when a complex phrase or a sentence can be parsed in more than one way. For example:

(1). - How do you stop a fish from smelling? - Cut off its nose. Two different grammatical structures of the given example can be parsed. In both cases the core importance is the word smelling in its different interpretations. Specifically, smelling means stink as well as to smell. Therefore, it is possible for one and the same sentence with the same structure to be interpreted in different ways as in the following example. How do you stop the fish from smelling?

1. How can we keep the fish from smelling ?
2. How can you stop the fish to smell?

Structural - semantic ambiguity arises when a word or concept has an inherently diffuse meaning based on its widespread or informal usage. This is often the case, for example, with idiomatic expressions whose definitions are rarely or never well-defined, and are presented in the context of a larger argument that invites a certain conclusion. For instance:

(1). - Did you take a bath? -No, only towels, is there one missing? (Take a bath), as a fixed phrase means to have a shower, but its direct, word for word translation can be - carry away a bath, to carry it from one place to another. This two-way perception and understanding of one and the same phrase creates ambiguity and causes laughter.

(2). -When do parents complain because of eye pain? - When they have their eye on you! In this specific example ambiguity is created by the phrase (to have an eye on). In the question the word eye implies the part of the body and the answer is quite incongruous. It can be

argued that this witty, unexpected answer together with the semantic ambiguity creates a structural-semantic pun.

The pun semantic structure are four fixed and two variable components:

- a) detail-logic;
- b) expressive and stylistic;
- c) an associative-shaped;
- d) functional;
- d) Background
- e) social and local.

In terms of accessories background component to one or another category of cultural information puns are divided into two types:

- a) a pun based on the facts constituting the information society's culture of social capital fund;
- b) puns with content related to current events and phenomena of mass culture.

The first type includes the following pun, built on the NCCA plays the name of Shakespeare's wife. It contains background information on the well-known circumstances of the marriage of the famous English playwright. "And, though he tried to marry someone else, she prevailed without need for eloquence. As St. Dedalus puts. Whoever has her Will, Ann hath a way (A. Burgess).

The second category of background puns different fragility background knowledge within their informative structure.

Puns of this kind are based on the names of statesmen and public figures of different ranks, and contain background knowledge, the durability of which depends on the role that these individuals play in social fluidity of the political life of the country, and the importance of the events recorded in the pun.

Field of semantic-stylistic propagation pun limited duration can vary from subject to base context (chapter, paragraph).

Thus, the content of the following pun Shakespeare is easily deduced from his micro context, and the scope of its semantic and stylistic spread that environment and limited: "Angelo ... Elbow is your name? Why dost thou not speak, Elbow? - Pompey. He can not, sir; he's out at elbow. "

In other cases, pun content may have an impact on the larger context of spatial characteristics.

Moreover, it can either be summarized content prior pun context (summarizing puns) "They occupied their time for two or three hundred years, in building Roman roads and having Roman baths. This was called the Roman occupation" (W. Sellar and R. Yestman), or to enter follow them context (non-productive puns) - "Crawling at you feet", said the Gnat ... you say observe a bread-and-butter-fly. Its wings are thin slices of bread-and-butter, its body is a crust, and its head is a lump of sugar ... "(L. Carroll).

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